

Модель организации патриотического воспитания обучающихся в системе преемственности «школа – вуз»

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. В условиях динамично меняющегося мира, когда глобализация и информационная открытость оказывают значительное влияние на сознание молодого поколения, проблема патриотического воспитания приобретает особую актуальность, решение которой видится в использовании потенциала системы преемственности между школой и вузом. **Цель исследования** – разработка и представление модели организации патриотического воспитания обучающихся в системе преемственности «школа – вуз».

Материалы и методы. Методологическая основа исследования: теоретические положения аксиологического, системно-деятельностного, целостного, средового подходов. Методы исследования: анализ нормативно-правовых документов; теоретический анализ научной литературы российских и зарубежных ученых по проблеме патриотического воспитания обучающихся, системы преемственности между школой и вузом; моделирование.

Результаты исследования. На основе результатов исследования разработана модель организации патриотического воспитания обучающихся в системе преемственности «школа – вуз», состоящая из пяти взаимодополняющих блоков: установочно-целевой, теоретико-методологический, содержательно-смысловой, организационно-технологический и критериально-результативный. Дана содержательная характеристика блоков модели, где рабочая программа воспитания рассмотрена как ведущий педагогический инструмент ее реализации через определенные виды деятельности и формы работы с обучающимися. Эффективность реализации модели можно отследить по включенности обучающихся на всех образовательных уровнях в гражданскую, национальную и культурную идентичность, что находит свое отражение в критериях и показателях.

Заключение. Внедрение модели организации патриотического воспитания обучающихся в системе преемственности «школа – вуз» предполагается успешным, если будут соблюдены организационно-педагогические условия (комплексное взаимодействие компонентов воспитывающей среды в системе преемственности «школа – вуз», использование потенциала историко-культурного наследия России и родного края в рамках учебной и внеучебной деятельности школы и вуза, взаимодействие всех участников образовательных отношений в системе «школа – вуз», в том числе сетевое) и этапы ее реализации (аналитический, методический, оценочный); для обеспечения устойчивости и повторяемости результатов будут подготовлены методические рекомендации по реализации данной модели, а также учебно-методическое пособие для педагогов школы и вуза по реализации регионального компонента в рамках изучения курса истории и литературы.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

преемственность, воспитывающая среда, патриотизм, патриотическое воспитание, модель патриотического воспитания, вуз, школа

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Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

Model for organizing patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. In the context of a dynamically changing world, where globalization and informational openness significantly influence the consciousness of the younger generation, the problem of patriotic education becomes particularly relevant. A solution is seen in utilizing the potential of the continuity system between school and university. The research aims to develop and present a model for organizing patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system.

Materials and methods. The methodological basis of the research includes theoretical principles of the axiological, system-activity, holistic, and environmental approaches. The research methods utilized in the research were as follows: analysis of regulatory legal documents; theoretical analysis of scientific literature by Russian and foreign scholars on the problem of patriotic education of students and the school-university continuity system; modeling.

Results. Based on the research findings, a model for organizing patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system has been developed. The model consists of five complementary blocks: conceptual and target block, theoretical and methodological block, content and semantic block, organizational and technological block, and criteria and performance block. A substantive description of the model's blocks is provided, where the curriculum for education is considered as the leading pedagogical tool for its implementation through specific types of activities and forms of work with students. The effectiveness of the model's implementation can be tracked by the involvement of students at all educational levels in civic, national, and cultural identity, which is reflected in the criteria and indicators.

Conclusion. The implementation of the model for organizing patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system is expected to be successful if the organizational and pedagogical conditions are met (comprehensive interaction of components of the nurturing environment within the school–university continuity system, utilization of the potential of Russia's historical and cultural heritage and that of the native region within the academic and extracurricular activities of schools and universities, interaction of all participants in educational relations within the school–university system, including network interaction) and its implementation stages (analytical, methodological, evaluative) are followed. In order to ensure the sustainability and reproducibility of the results, methodological recommendations for implementing this model will be prepared, as well as a teaching aid for school and university teachers on implementing the regional component within the study of history and literature courses.

KEYWORDS

continuity, nurturing environment, patriotism, patriotic education, model of patriotic education, university, school

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INTRODUCTION

UNESCO's recommendations on education for peace, human rights, and sustainable development – a normative document outlining how education should be used to achieve lasting peace and promote human development – present the concept of "*global citizenship education*." This system involves "learning about the impact of past and present events and conflicts, studying the economic, social and political interconnections between countries and societies, and fostering in learners empathy and respect for the diversity of cultures and opinions" [1].

The changing geopolitical situation – including the deterioration of the international environment, economic instability, attempts to distort historical data, and the imposition of moral norms and behavioral models alien to Russian culture – has a significant impact on all spheres of modern society. This necessitates an update of the substantive content of the education system, whose central tenet is patriotism as a factor of societal self-identification and consolidation.

Russian state policy defines new vectors for achieving the goals of patriotic education, which, in accordance with the National Security Strategy of the Russian Federation [2], is based on traditional Russian spiritual and moral values. The primary task of the modern Russian educational system is to "create conditions for nurturing a harmoniously developed, patriotic, and socially responsible individual, grounded in traditional Russian spiritual, moral, cultural, and historical values" [3]. The Federal State Educational Standard for Basic General Education (FSES BGE) also provides benchmarks for building an effective system of patriotic education, outlining clear expected outcomes for the civic, patriotic, spiritual, and moral... development of the individual [4].

Despite the priority status of state policy in the area of patriotic education, the question remains of building this process across all educational levels to ensure the sequential and systematic formation of patriotic values in the younger generation. This requires comprehensive interaction among various social institutions and civil society institutions. An analysis of existing educational practices (the experience of the Luhansk State Pedagogical University [5]; the implementation of patriotic education at the regional level [6]) suggests that a *continuous nurturing environment across educational institutions is an effective condition*. It is supposed that by laying the foundations of civic consciousness, respect for national traditions, history, culture, and the traditions of the multinational people of Russia at the school education level, the university then continues to develop these personal qualities, fostering a conscious attitude toward one's duties to society and the state. The purposeful work of the school teaching staff, and subsequently the university staff, involving the active engagement of students in socially beneficial activities while utilizing the capabilities of modern technologies and considering regional specifics and the historical-cultural heritage of their "small homeland" as organic components of the nurturing environment, will contribute to the development of not only educated specialists but also patriots of their country, ready to make a significant contribution to its development and prosperity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In scientific literature, continuity is examined from various perspectives: the philosophical aspect, within the framework of dialectical laws, particularly the law of the negation of the negation, where it is seen as "the connection between different stages or levels of development, the essence of which is the preservation of certain elements of the whole or its individual characteristics during the transition to a new state" [7]; the cultural studies aspect, where it is presented in the context of cultural heritage, social memory, and cultural development, ensuring the accumulation, storage, transmission, and transformation of socio-cultural experience [8]; in the research of Babić, within sociocultural development theory, where childhood is viewed as a sociocultural reality [9]; and the psychological aspect, which is revealed from the viewpoint of developmental psychology and the psychology of personality development [10]. In pedagogical research, continuity is considered both as a general pedagogical principle and as a condition for implementing the principles of scientific rigor, consistency, accessibility, and systematicity [11]; it is represented at horizontal (sequential study of material, coordination of content, forms, and methods) and vertical (preparation for the next educational stage) levels [12; 13].

Consequently, continuity serves as the connecting link that ensures the transmission of knowledge, experience, and values in intergenerational interaction, preserving cultural traditions and customs; it represents a stable connection between educational organizations, enabling a smooth transition from one level of learning to another.

When examining the theoretical foundations of the research problem, one should consider the position of Popov, who indicates that continuity between school and university education "includes unified educational content, forms, methods, and means; socio-psychological aspects of the moral development of the individual; psychological and pedagogical conditions for forming an active, creative personality; and objectivity in assessing the quality of knowledge of graduates from secondary educational institutions" [14, p. 329].

The viewpoint of foreign researchers on ensuring the school–university continuity system is also interesting (Bronkhorst, Akkerman): schools, by encouraging extracurricular activities, contribute to expanding students' opportunities, which is an important condition for establishing continuity in learning and preventing its interruption [15].

From the perspective of upbringing, the view of Senko is relevant today, considering continuity as a systematic interconnection between different stages in the development of a student's personal qualities, based on their moral experience, knowledge, skills, and abilities, with their expansion and deepening in subsequent periods of upbringing [16].

Continuity in upbringing, according to Zhukova, is a "process that ensures the success of upbringing at various stages of age development, promotes self-development, self-determination, and self-realization of the student, and is realized both vertically – involving the preservation of forms, methods, and techniques during the transition from one level of upbringing to another, from one stage of the educational system to another – and horizontally – oriented toward sequential age-related changes and developments in the child's personality, ensuring the successful formation of self-awareness, development of the emotional-sensual sphere, formation of labor and life skills, responsible personal behavior, and subsequent self-development of the personality" [17, p. 31].

It can be said that the *continuity of upbringing in the school–university system ensures connection* in the leading types of activities according to age periodization; in the goals, content, forms, and methods of implementing the educational process in school and university; in the forms of interaction among all subjects of educational relations aimed at creating favorable conditions for the emotional and social development of the individual; it presupposes a gradual transition of the student to a higher level of upbringing, where the conditions of upbringing change and, as a consequence, their worldview is restructured.

One of the worldview benchmarks at all levels of education is patriotism. Precisely patriotism, as a factor of self-identification and consolidation of society as a whole, forms a socially significant orientation in the individual at different educational levels, helps them find their role and place in society, and clearly defines life orientations.

In scientific literature, patriotism is considered from a philosophical standpoint as a component of cultural identity [18].

From a sociocultural perspective, it is studied as "one of the components of social consciousness, mentality, national self-awareness; as a component of ideology, culture, history, science; as one of the highest socially significant values; as a direction of upbringing; and as a source of well-being, prosperity, and successful development of the most important spheres of life" [19, p. 9]. This perspective aligns with the views of foreign researchers: in China, patriotism is considered as a traditional spirit of the Chinese nation and a long-term subject of ideological and political education in colleges and universities [20; 21]; studies examine the integration of the "Iron Man Spirit" (the core meaning of which can be summarized as "patriotism, entrepreneurship, realism, and devotion") into ideological and political education in colleges and universities [22]; the attitude toward the homeland is viewed through the lens of predetermining a person's character [23]; patriotic duty is studied as a traditional virtue of the Chinese nation, reflecting the close interconnection between the individual and the fate of the country [24]. In South Africa and the Dominican Republic, attention is paid to the effectiveness of the education system and public environment in developing a democratic culture among citizens [25]. Iceland et al. [26] conclude in their discussion that patriotism, or love

and devotion to one's country, can contribute to the formation of a civic culture that inspires people to work for the common good. The definition of "patriotism" also includes an individual's moral and cultural perception of their native land through "a person's understanding of their native history, culture, native language, natural and climatic environment, etc. In short, with everything that, transformed into images and key concepts, is encompassed by the notion of the Motherland" [27, p. 2]. This position is consistent with foreign research: a study of the life experiences of young people on Kulhudhuffushi Island in the Maldives and in Hamilton, New Zealand, showed that early exposure to the natural environment, social role models, and participation in actions contributed to the formation of an active civic position [28]. Maryna Kołeczek et al. [29] examine the relationship between constructive patriotism, glorification, and conventional patriotism with moral values and decisions. Adhering to the view of patriotism as a national and state idea of the unity and uniqueness of the people, Vyrshchikov considers the subject of patriotic education as "modeling (problematic) life situations that express the integrity of the country in (concrete) semantic, spiritual-cultural, value-based, and other manifestations, and organizing pedagogical conditions and means for their internal, emotional-semantic assimilation by students. The result of this assimilation should be an increase in the level and expansion of the scale of the 'we-identity' consciousness among children and youth" [30, p. 10].

According to Xiaohe Zeng [31], patriotic education is the ideological and political educational work carried out by the Party and the state, and its formative logic is primarily divided into three perspectives: historical origin, theoretical source, and practical basis.

Pascal Alscher et al. [32] believe that patriotic education plays a key role in the political life of youth, aiming to equip young people with the necessary competencies and skills for effective participation in political and civic life.

An analysis of scientific literature allows defining patriotism as a socio-historical phenomenon, predetermined by the socio-political and economic situation in the country. In modern conditions, where society requires clear benchmarks for forming its own identity, a deep and comprehensive understanding of the concept of "patriotism" acquires particular significance. Under these circumstances, it is the system of patriotic education, which establishes continuity across all educational levels, that will achieve a level of socialization where personal potential can be realized through service to the Motherland, a desire to contribute to the development of science and spiritual values, and an aspiration to feel pride in one's cultural and historical heritage. When examining the problem of implementing the principle of continuity in the system of patriotic education for students at different educational levels, a number of studies should be highlighted. Milkevich [33] defines the lines of continuity in patriotic education at various educational levels, differentiating its content and implementation technologies. Konnova and Konnova [34] present the experience of Tula State University regarding the continuity of traditions in fostering patriotism among students in secondary and higher education, which are transmitted to students in an interdisciplinary context through the study of history, economics, sociology, cultural studies, foreign languages, and other disciplines. Bukhavets [35] studies the problem of fostering patriotism among future police officers within various institutions (Yunarmiya, cadet and Suvorov schools, colleges, specialized law classes, and educational organizations of the Russian Ministry of Internal Affairs).. Zhdanova [36] presents the stages of implementing continuity in the formation of patriotism among students from grades 1 to 11. Muss [37] examines the problems of continuity in patriotic education between kindergarten and primary school. Evdokimova [38] discusses the unification of efforts by the family, kindergarten, supplementary education organizations, and cultural and art institutions in the development and education of a Noble Citizen in a child. Brian [39] examines partnerships between schools, families, and communities.

Analyzing the broad spectrum of scientific works on the problem, which contain valuable material, it is important to note that most of them focus on continuity at the kindergarten–primary school and primary school–secondary school levels. Regarding school–university continuity in the aspect of patriotic education, views on this problem through the prism of target orientations are of interest, where continuity is observed, reflected in the educational programs at both school and university levels. At the university level, an expansion of the range of tasks related to the formation of a civic position is indicated, within the framework of both academic disciplines and extracurricular activities. Despite positive developments, including the active integration of the educational component into the education system at all levels, it should be noted that no research has been found presenting a holistic, sequential organization of the patriotic education process. This organization would be reflected not only in the continuity of educational levels within the school–university interaction system but also

in the creation of a specific, unified nurturing environment embedded in the target foundations of this process, its substantive basis, and its technological and performance characteristics. Such research would also summarize the forms of interaction and types of activities that promote the inclusion of students in various types of identity – civic, cultural, national, and social.

Thus, this research is aimed at developing and presenting a model for organizing patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The following theoretical methods were used to study the problem field of the research: analysis of regulatory legal documents and scientific literature. Particular attention was paid to scientific publications indexed in the Web of Science and Scopus bibliographic databases, as well as the Russian Science Citation Index (RSCI), which allowed for the refinement of the key concept definitions for the research. Based on theoretical modeling, an original model for organizing the patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system was designed. Its structure was predicated on the principle that a "model of pedagogical activity included the concept of the expected result, the determination of its meaning, the characteristics of the means and conditions necessary for achieving the expected result, and specified the subjects of the activity" [40, p. 89]. The methodological foundation for developing the model consisted of the axiological, system-activity, holistic, and environmental approaches.

RESULTS

A review of scientific and methodological literature on the research problem allowed designing a model for organizing the patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system (Fig. 1). The model comprises five complementary blocks: *the conceptual and target block*, *the theoretical and methodological block*, *the content and semantic block*, *the organizational and technological block*, and *the criteria and performance block*.

CONCEPTUAL AND TARGET BLOCK defines the general logic for organizing the process of patriotic education for students. This logic consists of implementing organizational and pedagogical conditions that ensure a stable system of value-based and semantic orientations of a patriotic nature across the school–university educational levels. This is achieved through the creation of a continuous nurturing environment within educational institutions.

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BLOCK. The *axiological approach* holds a central place in the model. It implies a conscious influence on the process of forming an individual's value attitudes and moral principles, which collectively determine the value-based, semantic, and normative-regulatory mechanism of their life. This approach makes it possible, while adhering to the principle of continuity within the school–university system, to determine the optimal selection of pedagogical resources aimed at shaping students' basic national values and to outline prospects for improving the system of patriotic education.

The ideas of the *system-activity approach* allow for the consideration of the educational process as an interaction and interconnection of all constituent components of the system, and as a necessary condition for the active, independent involvement of students in various types of activities. In this context, maintaining continuity in the school–university system, which considers the content, forms, methods, and techniques of educational work, becomes particularly important. This approach also helps define the criteria for evaluating the results of patriotic education, where the activity aspect, alongside value orientations and semantic attitudes, will manifest in real actions, practical deeds, and conduct.

The *holistic approach* is an extension of the system-activity approach, enhancing the content of the process under investigation. It involves reorienting the younger generation from the values of "consumers" to the values of "creators" at all educational levels, which will make them spiritually rich and, most importantly, individuals with value-based semantic orientations.

Figure 1 Model for organizing patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system

The *environmental approach* provides an opportunity to consider the environment as a condition functioning as an intermediary. A continuous nurturing environment plays a key role in transforming the curriculum for education into a planning tool that contributes to achieving the goal of the patriotic education model for students. Within the model, the environmental approach determines the purposeful use of the nurturing environment's potential in the pedagogical process, its conversion into a means of pedagogical influence, and the consideration of all the environment's capabilities.

The presented approaches are implemented through the following principles: *the principle of value priority*, which allows for the realization of the nurturing environment's potential through values, representable as stages of mastering these values at all educational levels; *the principle of cultural conformity*, which serves as the basis for constructing the concept of educational work at all educational levels, implying the creation of conditions for the cultural development of students; *the principle of continuity, defined by us as a priority*, which presupposes the preservation of the components of the educational process (subjects, goals, content, means, results) and the strengthening of its foundations during the transition from one educational level to another; *the principle of regulating the nurturing environment*, which programs the nature of the educational process based on key cultural and semantic aspects, and allows for the consideration of the nurturing environment's potential in accordance with the interests and needs of the subjects of educational relations.

CONTENT AND SEMANTIC BLOCK. The continuity system is presented at two levels: vertical – presupposing continuity in the goals, content of educational activities, forms, and methods at the school–university educational levels, reflected in the semantic and value content of the curriculum for education; and horizontal – accounting for the sequential development of the personality, the "accumulation" of positive qualities, and self-development under the influence of the educational organization's nurturing environment. This integration of levels ensures the integrity and systematic nature of the patriotic education process.

This block reveals the potential of the curriculum for education as the leading pedagogical tool for implementing the model, allowing teaching staff to determine the content, types, and forms of educational activities. This occurs on the platform of a unified value basis, considering current social requirements for the student's personality and the priorities of the Russian state's educational policy. The modular architecture of the curriculum for education ensures the sequential development of the educational process across all areas of educational work, providing the opportunity to "fill" the content of each module in accordance with a specific educational level. Essentially, with each educational level, a semantic enlargement of the module occurs, which allows speaking of continuity in this document.

It is worth noting that patriotic education holds a leading place both in the target orientations and the description of the educational organization's way of life, as well as in the substantive content of the modules of the curriculum for education at all levels:

- *the subject-aesthetic environment of a patriotic nature* is expressed through the use of state symbols of the Russian Federation (the national flag, emblem, and anthem). The flag-raising ceremony enhances the importance of national symbols as emblems of unity, identity, and pride, which contributes to the development of an emotional connection with their country's heritage and a deep sense of patriotism in students at all educational levels;
- *the introduction of the cycle of classes "Conversations about Important Things"* into extracurricular activities, covering a wide range of civic and patriotic topics, including historical insights, emphasizes to students the importance of civic duties and the role of national symbols. This cycle of classes is implemented both in schools and in pedagogical universities, which allows considering these classes as a connecting element ensuring continuity, significantly enriching the value-based semantic sphere of the individual, both for the younger generation and future teachers;
- *student participation in creating civic-patriotic and local history clubs* allows them to study the history of their family and native region, participate in local history expeditions, engage in search work, and create projects dedicated to preserving historical and cultural heritage.

Within this block of the model, the forms of interaction and types of activities used in the implementation of the curriculum for education have been defined. Their effectiveness is determined

by considering the substantive content of the components of the continuous nurturing environment, as well as the participation of all subjects of educational relations in activities aimed at assimilating values of a spiritual and moral nature.

ORGANIZATIONAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL BLOCK. The conceptual-target and content-semantic blocks of the model are effectively implemented in practice within a specific nurturing environment, which establishes a number of *organizational and pedagogical conditions*.

Comprehensive interaction of the components of the nurturing environment within the school–university continuity system.

A nurturing environment, specially created for the individual, has a purposeful and positive influence on the process of personality development. Vygotsky spoke about its significant impact on the individual, asserting that it is the "main lever of the educational process" [10, p. 83].

Regarding *the school's nurturing environment*, it represents "the totality of circumstances surrounding the child, which are socially valuable, influence their personal development, and facilitate their integration into modern culture"; it "includes the subject-spatial surroundings, the behavioral environment of the school, the event-based surroundings, and the informational-cultural surroundings" [42, p. 97].

The university's nurturing environment combines sociocultural and value factors that influence the student's personality by immersing them in a subject-aesthetic environment that contributes to the enrichment of their inner world and the creation of an atmosphere of psychological comfort; a content-rich system of interaction that creates a value-based semantic field of communication; and a value-activity system of relations that forms a regulatory mechanism for life.

Continuity in patriotic education between school and university implies the creation of a unified nurturing environment where values, attitudes, and traditions organically transition from one educational level to another. This facilitates the actualization of socially significant values and their integration into the individual's worldview structure. The organization of such an environment is achieved by involving students in active endeavors, such as: socio-cultural cross-age practices; volunteer work; military-sports games; patriotic quests and web-quests; research and search competitions; youth patriotic forums; maintaining blogs on patriotic themes; historical, literary, and art history tours created by university students for school students, among others. The educational potential of these forms of active student engagement is substantially supplemented and expanded by a new area of pedagogical practice in the Russian university system – "Service-Learning," which allows students to address socially significant tasks within their field of specialty. The integration of this discipline into university curricula involves performing socially beneficial initiatives in real-world practice based on NGOs, charitable foundations, and volunteer associations. "Service-Learning" will soon be incorporated into the educational process of all Russian schools as well, which will enable building continuity between university and school through the implementation of joint projects. These projects should be reflected in the annual plans for educational work of the educational organizations.

Utilization of the potential of Russia's historical and cultural heritage, and that of the native region, within the academic and extracurricular activities of school and university.

The development of universal human values, particularly national self-awareness and patriotic feelings, is impossible without studying the history, culture, and literature of one's native region. The FGOS BGE highlights "understanding literature as one of the basic national-cultural values of the people, as a special way of cognizing life" as one of the subject-specific results [4]. Works by regional writers help students understand the specifics of both the historical time and the geographical and cultural space of their native land. The reflection in literature of the realities of life of people living in a specific area, the recreation of their customs and traditions, undoubtedly evokes a sense of connection to the events described and contributes to the formation of a caring attitude towards one's roots, and hence, to the cultivation of patriotic feelings.

One of the most effective ways to learn about the history of one's country and "small homeland" is military-patriotic tourism. Its potential not only deepens students' knowledge about the history of a city but also provides an opportunity to use this knowledge to analyze the past, shaping their worldview. Excursion programs (in both offline and online formats) to various cities allow for a clearer

representation of events that took place on Russian soil, both during the Great Patriotic War and in the modern world.

Interaction of all participants in educational relations within the school–university system, including network interaction.

The community formed through the interaction of all subjects of the educational process creates a certain unity, which acts as a source and resource for the value-based semantic development of each of them through communication with representatives of different generations. In such a system of interaction, social partners play an important role; these can include scientific pedagogical communities; children's movements (Yunarmiya, "Movement of the First," "Big Break," "Volunteers of Victory," etc.); institutions for children's and teenagers' leisure and recreation; cultural institutions; physical culture and sports institutions; NGOs, etc.

In the context of continuity, the participation of schools and universities in network events aimed at designing the nurturing environment through the use of partners' resources as well as creating online communities with a patriotic agenda should be discussed; it is necessary for schoolchildren and students to become active subjects of network events by participating in their preparation and conduct.

The ORGANIZATIONAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL BLOCK is characterized by the implementation of three stages in organizing the system of patriotic education.

The analytical stage involves the establishment of a scientific center for methodological support of educational activities at the university, which will include leading university specialists in education and educational advisors. Within the center's activities, at both the university and general school levels, a survey of students is organized to diagnose the level of formed basic knowledge and understanding of the state structure, culture, and history of Russia; the degree of expression of positive emotions and feelings associated with belonging to Russian society; the manifestation of an active civic position and participation in volunteer and patriotic campaigns; mastery of behavioral norms corresponding to the requirements of patriotic education; and readiness to take responsibility for one's own actions. The results are analyzed and discussed by the center's staff to build a strategy for implementing the system of patriotic education. A survey of school and university teachers is conducted to identify problematic areas in the organization of patriotic education and for the subsequent development of professional development courses for them. The center assesses the quality of the continuous nurturing environment within the school–university system, identifying its deficits and potential in the patriotic education system, and revealing "obstacles" for school students continuing their trajectory of development as responsible citizens at the university level.

At this stage, it is necessary to build interaction between the Vice-Rector for Education and Youth Policy and the educational advisors. The result of this interaction should be the creation of unified requirements for the content and implementation of the curriculum for education; the systematization of best practices in the field of education, whose innovative elements will help identify effective methods and means for implementing patriotic education; such cooperation will also contribute to building partnerships with public associations and social partners.

The methodological stage involves the creation of a unified subject-spatial environment; and the methodological support of the patriotic education system, taking into account the characteristics of generations and the changing information environment [43; 44]. This stage implies the sequential immersion of the student (depending on the educational level) into the processes of perceiving, comprehending, and assimilating those traits, characteristics, and meanings associated with the history, culture, and life of the Russian people and state. The primary goals of this identification are mastering the basic facts and events of Russian history; forming a positive self-assessment of one's own citizenship and belonging to Russian civilization; assimilating the moral and ethical norms characteristic of Russian society; and fostering pride in the achievements of ancestors and contemporaries. Such identification is achieved through the implementation of modules of the curriculum for education and the presented organizational-pedagogical conditions. The effectiveness of identification is achieved through the use of various forms of interaction and types of activities adapted to the characteristics of the students' age group.

The *evaluative stage* is aimed at creating a unified system for assessing the effectiveness of educational work at all levels of education. This system includes clear and measurable criteria reflecting

the goals and objectives of the educational process; it provides for a feedback and adjustment mechanism. The criteria must consider the age characteristics of students, the specifics of the educational organization, and current social challenges. The evaluation results should be used to make changes to the curricula for education, as well as for the professional development of teaching staff. An integral part of the unified assessment system is its integration into the overall education quality management system. This implies aligning the goals and indicators of educational work with other aspects of the educational organization's activities, such as teaching and methodological, research, and administrative work. It is important to create a unified information space that ensures the accessibility and efficiency of data exchange between different management levels.

The CRITERIA AND PERFORMANCE BLOCK of the model contains the criteria, indicators, and levels that allow for the assessment of the results of its practical implementation.

DISCUSSION

The results of the theoretical research, which enabled the construction of a logical framework for organizing the patriotic education of students, contribute new knowledge to the field of continuity in patriotic education within the school–university system of interaction, as well as to the creation of a unified nurturing environment as an effective condition.

It has been determined that *the curriculum for education is the leading pedagogical instrument* influencing the establishment of continuity in patriotic education within the school–university interaction system. This aspect is highlighted in the research of Borisova et al. [45], who note the particular significance of the potential of the target section of the curriculum for education, which is oriented toward forming value-based and goal-oriented foundations. The content of these foundations is built upon Russian basic constitutional and traditional spiritual-moral values, as well as the cultural-historical traditions of the peoples of Russia. The conclusion of this research on the continuity of the curriculum for education between school and university is supported by the study of Bugrov [46], who asserts that a number of areas of educational work are consistent across both school and university; furthermore, the pedagogical technologies implemented within educational activities, while not entirely identical, share similarities. The effectiveness of the specific *forms of interaction and types of activities* identified in the model for implementing the curriculum for education is also corroborated by the results of scientific research. Kazarenkov [47] demonstrates the importance of using university facilities and resources to organize physics and technical clubs and societies for school students. Murzina [48] points to the positive effects of student participation in virtual projects, military-sports games, and social practices. Shutenko et al. [49] and Lau et al. [50] identify the pedagogical potential and prove the effectiveness of volunteer activities. Research by Le et al. [51] indicates that students acquire civic views by emulating their parents, underscoring the link between parental social responsibility and that of adolescents. The work of Amal Musa Alrashidi et al. [52] and Iana Tzankova et al. [53] emphasizes the proven effectiveness of activities such as cultural programs, community work, scouting, and social clubs, which are identified as key mechanisms for value transmission. Evidence supporting the success of project-based activities in the patriotic education of students is presented in the work of Lee Jerome et al. [54]. Thus, the curriculum for education is a necessary pedagogical tool that ensures the targeted and systematic interaction of all subjects of educational relations, aimed at forming the personality of a Russian citizen based on the values, attitudes, and qualities enshrined in the Russian Constitution, considering the necessity of their realization in modern conditions. Through a well-structured system for implementing the curriculum for education, a regional nurturing environment with its own specificities, traditions, and educational practices is created within the educational organization. An important aspect of the presented model is its substantiated *organizational and pedagogical conditions*. Their rationality and logic align with a number of research findings. For instance, *the organization of a continuous nurturing environment with a patriotic focus* is achieved by involving students in active endeavors, particularly through their engagement in projects within the discipline of "Service-Learning". This research agrees with the viewpoint of a number of contemporary researchers who indicate that service-learning enhances empathy in the younger generation (Gordon et al. [55]); connects theory and practice, providing students with the opportunity both to participate in service that meets community needs and to reflect on their experience (Resch, Schrittester) [56]; and fosters social activity manifested in responsibility, compassion, and

selflessness (Harkins et al.) [57]; (Haynes) [58]. Research proves that involving students in social practices helps "form such a predictor of prosocial behavior as civic optimism. It is expressed in their confidence that the implemented social projects make a visible contribution to the development of society as a whole and its specific social groups" [59, p. 24]. Resch and Schritteser emphasize the importance of integrating service-learning into teacher education and the value of professional development for teachers in this area [60], which confirms our considerations regarding the significance of this discipline for the patriotic education of the younger generation.

Consequently, by creating a nurturing environment that unites school and university through the interaction of its components – such as a subject space with a patriotic orientation, meaningful event-based interaction, and the involvement of students at all educational levels in active endeavors – a sense of belonging to Russian culture is actualized among the subjects of the educational organization. Behavioral moral-ethical regulators (such as honor, justice, duty, etc.) are formed, and the uniqueness of this environment as part of the historical and cultural heritage of the "small homeland" is comprehended. This serves as the primary condition for the effective patriotic education of the individual.

The utilization of the potential of Russia's historical and cultural heritage, and that of the native region, within the academic and extracurricular activities of school and university is a leading condition of the model. This aligns with the position of Antonov, who notes that when reading works by regional writers, a "feeling of recognition emerges, which is crucial for perception. This is a cultural code shared by the writer and the reader. Herein lies the preservation of culture, nature, monuments, language, customs, and habits – those very spiritual bonds that everyone seeks but struggles to establish across a vast and diverse country, a country that cannot be reliably consolidated without these very bonds at the regional level. This is the purpose and importance of 'small' regional literature" [61, p. 141].

The significance of studying regional history and its influence on the formation of civic patriotic consciousness is confirmed by both foreign and Russian research. Yeniay Üsküplü argues that Turkey is currently attempting to achieve a political balance through history education, which is directly linked to a sense of belonging and is aimed at shaping the future [62; 63]. Bolotova and Tretyak have identified forms of interaction between subjects of the educational and cultural space in implementing the regional component of history education: developing projects for excursion routes in Volgograd and the region, writing essays based on provided statements about the Great Patriotic War, a competition for methodological developments among teachers titled "Lesson of the Stalingrad Victory," creating documentary films on regional history, among others [64].

Thus, the creation of an educational-upbringing and socio-cultural space provides an opportunity to involve students in educational, excursion-local history, and various types of leisure activities. Through these activities, the transmission of cultural experience, the formation of social norms and relationships, and orientation towards universal human values are performed. Regarding *the interaction of all participants in educational relations within the school–university system, including network interaction*, it should be noted that a number of scientific studies point to the effectiveness of a system of patriotic education for the younger generation that is adapted to the realities of network interaction and utilizes digital platforms and communication channels. Kulikova and Fomenko state that "previously, a child from a small town or a remote village did not have the opportunity to familiarize themselves broadly with the activities of key foundations in their country, communicate with figures from the army and culture, sports and politics, or transfer a symbolic sum of one ruble for medical aid to veterans by lighting an online 'candle of memory'; now they have this opportunity thanks to digital technologies" [65, p. 18]. Fedorova et al. state that the modern approach to the civic-patriotic education of students involves the use of new technologies that meet their interests and preferences, such as 3D games, tele-tandems, podcasts, social networks, video resources, and other innovative technologies [66]. Woods et al. indicate that digital technologies have created a new universal space for social consciousness, identity, belonging, and collective action [67]. Hahn et al. [68] prove that younger adolescents can derive various moral lessons from narrative media content. The study by Makeela et al. [69] on the influence of patriotism on the institutional foundation and on Social Entrepreneurial Orientation (SEO), which contributes to the improvement of social welfare activities through socially friendly business and commercial organizations, is interesting for this research. This finding indicates the importance of interaction between schools and universities with institutional partners. Consequently, through a balance in the goal-setting and content of patriotic

education tasks, as well as coordinated work at all educational levels, the presented organizational and pedagogical conditions will allow for the enrichment of the value-based semantic sphere of all subjects of educational relations by creating a continuous nurturing environment within the school–university system of interaction.

CONCLUSION

In summary, it is important to note that *the potential of a continuous nurturing environment across educational organizations, in the aspect of patriotic education*, is expressed in the creation of a holistic value-based semantic field. This field is grounded in established traditional Russian spiritual and moral values, which are formed across all educational levels. The integration of these values into the students' worldview system and their actualization through various types of activities and forms of interaction will enable students to build a life strategy oriented toward creation, service to society, and the preservation of cultural heritage. The awareness and acceptance of these values will help students feel a connection with previous generations, creating a solid foundation for developing a sense of patriotism, civic responsibility, and a readiness to contribute to the prosperity of Russian society.

The presented findings are reflected in the developed model for organizing the patriotic education of students within the school–university continuity system of interaction. The model includes the following blocks: the conceptual and target block (defines the general logic for organizing the process of patriotic education for students at the school–university educational levels); the theoretical and methodological block (includes the rationale for the methodological approaches and principles); the content and semantic block (reveals the potential of the curriculum for education as the leading pedagogical tool through forms of interaction and types of activity proven effective by pedagogical practice); the organizational and technological block (demonstrated through the content of organizational-pedagogical conditions; defines the stages of model implementation); and the criteria and performance block (presents indicators and criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the continuous nurturing environment of schools and universities in the aspect of patriotic education).

The practical significance and prospects of the research lie in the possibility of implementing this model for organizing patriotic education within the school–university nurturing environment continuity system in various educational organizations across the country, taking into account the specifics of studying regional literature and utilizing the potential of the region's historical and cultural heritage. In order to ensure the sustainability and reproducibility of the results, methodological recommendations for implementing this model are being developed, as well as a teaching aid for school and university teachers on implementing the regional component within the study of history courses.

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